

TRADITIONAL METHODS OF WHEAT BREEDING

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Received: May 04, 2021; Accepted: May 13, 2021

Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum spp.* L.) is the oldest cereal crop and is cultivated in a wide variety of weather and soil conditions. It thrives in temperate climates with annual rainfall of 30–90 cm. Wheat is grown mostly in South Asia. There are several *Triticum* species, each with a unique genome and chromosome number. Wheat belongs to the genus *Triticum*, tribe Triticeae, family Poaceae (Gramineae), and order Cyperales, and is a self-pollinated crop. Traditional plant breeding is important for introducing novel alleles by crossing genotypes from various plant genetic resources, such as modern varieties with locally-adapted varieties, to increase genetic diversity and selection for desired traits such as high grain yield, early maturing, improved grain quality, and resistance to lodging, biotic and abiotic stresses. While plant breeders and geneticists are interested in modern wheat biotechnology techniques that use advanced DNA sequences and molecular methods, conventional plant breeding methods are still the most important and first step in developing new wheat cultivars with desirable traits. Plant breeders use many conventional breeding techniques for crop enhancement, the most common of which are pedigree breeding, pure line breeding, bulk breeding, mass selection, single seed descent, and backcross breeding for wheat (Baenziger *et al.*, 2016). The inbreeding of the population and the selection process are two significant factors that influence breeding practises.

Pedigree Breeding: Wheat breeders use this approach to test F₂ plants for target traits and choose the best plants from this generation. In a progeny chain, the chosen seeds are grown in the next generation. The best plants are chosen from among the grown plants. Each generation, the selection is carried out until there is some segregation within the progeny lines. Many factors influence segregation within a row, including the number of segregating characteristics in the sample population, the number of inbred generations, and phenotypic results.

Pure-Line Breeding: A number of selected individual plants from a cultivar are grown in rows and the best rows are chosen in this breeding process. Finally, replicates of the best rows are grown to determine which selection is the most promising (Baenziger *et al.*, 2016).

Traditional Breeding Methods

Fig.1: conventional and modern methods of plant breeding.

Bulk Breeding: The majority of the progeny resulting from a single cross is grown by wheat breeders. The bulk seed is then harvested and a portion of it is planted again the next year. When the population comprises a mixture of mainly homozygous lines, which occurs after several plantings and harvestings of the bulk, the population is reconsidered (Tee *et al.*, 1975 and Qualset *et al.*, 1975).

Mass Selection: The most basic tool for crop enhancement is mass selection. Plants with a related phenotype are selected in large numbers by breeders. To create the new cultivar, seeds from various plants are mixed together. This approach yielded a cultivar with a lot of genetic diversity. As a result, mass selection may be done on such a cultivar once more (Marais *et al.*, 2009 and Botes *et al.*, 2009).

Single Seed Descent: This method's main aim is to quickly inbreed without using artificial or natural selection. In an F₂ population, wheat breeders start with a large number of plants. Then a single seed is sown from each plant. A single seed is planted and sown the next year. Every year, wheat breeders reap and sow the single seed until all plants are predominantly homozygous. Normally, no selection is made at this stage (Pignone *et al.*, 2015).

Backcross Breeding: Backcross techniques are used to simply integrate target inherited traits from unadopted donor genotypes into recipient genotypes. Backcross strategies include crossing to the receiver genotype (recurrent parent) several times, then selecting the trait of interest to be passed (Kenaschuk *et al.*, 1975). Breeders cross the F1 to a single cultivar with a strong character that could be applied again and again. This approach was commonly used to migrate a variety of desirable traits, such as disease tolerance. Some stem, leaf, and stripe rust resistance genes, for example, have been transferred from *Triticum* species to common wheat (Marais *et al.*, 2003). The backcross system was used to increase winter wheat resistance to *Fusarium* head blight (Clark *et al.*, 2016).

Conclusion

Traditional plant breeding approaches are still the primary and first points to produce new wheat cultivars with desirable traits, despite the fact that modern plant breeding using advancements in DNA technology has attracted wheat breeders and geneticists. The primary goal of traditional wheat breeding is to create a plant that can efficiently grow and flourish in a variety of environments. Changes in arable land, harsh cropping regimes, and food stability, as well as evolving global challenges, should all be taken into account (Davis *et al.*, 2004). These global problems can be solved in wheat by using plant breeding methods that allow for the selection of genotypes with suitable genes/QTLs.

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